

photometrically as already reported⁵. Present studies also confirm the data reported in the literature. Cobalt(II) also can be extracted quantitatively in the pH range 5.5 to 7.3.

(B) *Metals with the maximum percentage extraction of 50% and above but less than 100%*: The metals in this category are calcium(II), lanthanum(III), aluminium(III), thorium(IV), zirconium(IV), uranium(VI), molybdenum(VI) and tungsten(VI).

The pH extraction curves are given in Figs. 2 and 3, from which it is clear that the metal extraction increases as the pH increased except in the case of molybdenum(VI) and tungsten(VI). Tungsten(VI) extraction decreased as the pH increased, perhaps due to the formation of polytungstic acids in the aqueous phase. In the extraction of molybdenum(VI), first the metal extraction decreased up to pH 2.0 and then increased as the pH increased. This behaviour may be due to the formation of different species of molybdenum at pH less than 2 when it exists essentially as H_2MO_4 according to Stary¹, and as some different species at pH above 2. In the case of calcium(II), thorium(IV) and aluminium(III), there was initial extraction but above certain pH values, there was slight precipitation. Therefore the extraction curves could not be plotted for the entire pH range.

(C) *Metals with the maximum percentage extraction of less than 50%*: The metals studied under this category are ferrous and ferric iron, manganese(II), beryllium(II) and chromium(III). The pH variation curves of these metals are shown in Fig. 4. Even when the equilibration time was prolonged to 12 hr in case of beryllium(II) and chromium(III), no significant extraction took place. In case of manganese(II), colour developed immediately which faded out in a few minutes. In case of iron(II) and iron(III), the spectrophotometric studies could not be performed at pH higher than 4.0 as there was precipitation.

Silver(I): Systematic studies of solvent extraction could not be carried out as the distribution ratios obtained by spectrophotometric methods were not reproducible due to absorption of silver ions on glass vessel. As there was no facility to determine the distribution ratios by radiometric method, the investigations are incomplete.

From the above study it can be seen that salicylidene amino thiophenol would be effective in the solvent extraction of various metals discussed above. Detailed investigations will be published subsequently.

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Detection and Chromatographic Separation of Phenols on Papers Impregnated with Ferric Hydroxide

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THE use of chromatographic papers loaded with Amberlite ion exchange resin has been reported by Clark¹. Scant attention has been paid on the chromatography of phenols on papers impregnated with inorganic ion exchangers. Use of papers impregnated with stannic molybdate, has been made in our laboratory for the separation of phenols².

Experimental

Preparation of ion exchange papers: Whatman No. 3 paper strips of size 14 × 3 cm were dipped in 0.1 M ferric nitrate solution for 15-20 sec and then dried at room temperature. These paper strips were then dipped in 0.1 M sodium hydroxide solution for 40-45 sec. The excess of reagent was drained off and the strips were dried at room temperature over the filter sheets. These treated strips were washed twice with demineralized water to remove the excess of reagent. Finally, the strips were dried again at room temperature and used as such for chromatography.

Procedure: One or two spots of test solution in ethanol were placed on the paper strip with the help of a glass capillary. The paper was conditioned for 15 min and then solvent was allowed to ascend 11 cm in every case using 20 × 5 cm glass jars.

Results and Discussion

Detection: The colours observed with the phenols are listed below:

β -Hydroxy benzoic acid, β -naphthol, vanilline, *p*-nitrophenol, *m*-cresol, *p*-cresol, *o*-nitrophenol, picric acid, phloroglucinol, 4-(4-nitrophenyl)-azo resorcinol, di-(2-hydroxyphenylimino) ethane, 4-chlorophenol and 4-(2-pyridilazo) resorcinol gave yellow spots.

Tannic acid, α -naphthol, pyrogallol, resorcinol, catechol, gallic acid and xlenol gave violet spots.

2,4-Dinitrophenol, phenol, quinol and 8-hydroxy-7-iodoquinoline-5-sulphonic acid gave red spots.

Thymol blue, 1,2,5,8-hydroxyanthraquinone and phenyl fluorone, (9-phenyl-2,3,7-trihydroxy-6-fluorone), appeared as grey spots.

1-Nitroso-2-naphthol and bromocresol gave green spots.

TABLE 1— R_f VALUES OF PHENOLS ON FERRIC HYDROXIDE PAPERS IN WATER, SODIUM NITRATE (1.0 M, 0.1 M, 0.01 M), SODIUM CHLORIDE, ALCOHOL AND ALCOHOL+WATER (1:1) SYSTEMS

Sl. No.	Phenol	Water	1.0 M NaNO ₃	0.1 M NaNO ₃	0.01 M NaNO ₃	1.0 M NaCl	Alcohol	Alcohol+water (1:1)
1.	β -Hydroxy benzoic acid	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2.	Tannic acid	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.86	1.00
3.	Phloroglucinol	0.00	0.65	0.75	0.72	0.71	0.48	0.75
4.	α -Naphthol	0.50	0.54	0.36	0.36	0.00	0.90	0.72
5.	β -Naphthol	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
6.	p -Hydroxy benzoic acid	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
7.	Pyrogallol	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.27
8.	2,4-Dinitrophenol	0.31	0.46	0.36	0.34	0.56	0.32	0.63
9.	p -Nitrophenol	0.81	0.73	0.72	0.72	0.67	0.81	0.00
10.	Catechol	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
11.	m -Cresol	0.09	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.89	0.66
12.	p -Cresol	0.00	0.77	0.45	0.40	0.00	0.97	0.00
13.	Phenol	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.86
14.	Resorcinol	0.00	0.77	0.76	0.72	0.70	0.72	0.00
15.	Gallic acid	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.82
16.	o -Nitrophenol	0.81	0.75	0.79	0.60	0.00	0.45	0.27
17.	1-Nitroso-2-naphthol	0.72	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.81	0.81
18.	Xylenol	0.81	0.65	0.50	0.45	0.18	0.72	0.90
19.	Quinhydrone	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.91	0.81
20.	Quinol	0.00	0.76	0.80	1.00	0.00	0.90	0.81
21.	Picric acid	0.73	0.60	0.56	0.60	0.57	0.60	0.83
22.	Vanilline	0.00	0.59	0.59	0.54	0.05	0.80	0.95
23.	Thymol blue	0.82	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00
24.	1,2,5,8-Anthroxy anthraquinone	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.68
25.	4-(4-Nitrophenyl)-azo resorcinol	0.18	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.61	0.54
26.	Di-(2-hydroxyphenylimino) ethane	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.61	0.54
27.	8-Hydroxy-7-iodoquinoline-5-sulphonic acid	0.13	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.56	0.00
28.	Phenylfluorone (9-phenyl-2,3,7-trihydroxy-6-fluorone)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
29.	Trihydroxy-6-fluorone	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.27	0.00	1.00
30.	4-Chlorophenol	0.54	0.50	0.54	0.81	0.62	0.91	0.81
31.	Bromocresol green	0.82	0.67	0.86	0.68	0.59	0.65	0.81

The detection of phenols using ferric hydroxide impregnated papers can be made without the use of a separate detecting reagent for chromatographic studies.

Chromatography: 31 phenols were chromatographed in aqueous solution of sodium nitrate (1.0 M, 0.1 M, 0.01 M), water, alcohol, water + alcohol (1:1) and NaCl (1.0 M). The R_f values in different solvent systems are presented in Table 1.

The important separations of phenols were achieved on the basis of difference in R_f values in different solvent systems, e.g. α -naphthol from β -naphthol, 2,4-dinitrophenol from o -nitrophenol, 4-chlorophenol from phenol, picric acid from 2,4-dinitrophenol, catechol from quinol, pyrogallol from resorcinol, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol from α -naphthol, 4-(4-nitrophenyl)-azo resorcinol from resorcinol in 0.1 M NaNO₃; m -cresol from α -naphthol in 0.01 M NaNO₃; phloroglucinol from pyrogallol in 1.0 M NaCl; and o -nitrophenol from p -nitrophenol in alcohol solvent system as binary separations, and picric acid from 2,4-dinitrophenol and catechol, α -naphthol from β -naphthol and resorcinol, o -nitrophenol from picric acid and 2,4-dinitrophenol and bromocresol from vanilline and di-(2-hydroxyphenylimino) ethane as ternary separations in 0.1 M NaNO₃ solvent system.

The time required for the ascend of the solvent to a height of 11 cm was approximately 30 min. This shows the importance of the ferric hydroxide papers using simple aqueous systems and thus achieving clean separations in a short period. The use of ferric hydroxide increases the compactness of the spots and removes the tailings, which are commonly observed with plain papers in these simple solvent systems. Ferric hydroxide³ being a weak inorganic ion exchanger shows a selectivity towards the various phenols which are weakly ionized. This fact gives the basis for separations.

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